

RESEARCH ARTICLE

PRELIMINARY PERFORMANCE OF *RHIZOBIUM TROPICI* AND *BACILLUS SAFENSIS* ON AGRO-WASTE SUBSTRATES: VIABILITY AND ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY AS ALTERNATIVES TO SOIL-CHARCOAL CARRIER

¹*Sarah B. Aquino and ²Larjan Kent M. Cuevas

¹Chemist III, Department of Agriculture – Regional Field Office 02, Ilagan Soil Laboratory, Isabela, Philippines;

²Project Assistant III, Department of Agriculture Regional Field Office 02, Ilagan Soil Laboratory, Isabela, Philippines

ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 09th April, 2025

Received in revised form

21st May, 2025

Accepted 19th June, 2025

Published online 30th July, 2025

Keywords:

Rhizobium tropici, *Bacillus Safensis*, Biofertilizer Carriers, Agro-Waste, Microbial Viability, Cost-Benefit Analysis, Sustainable Agriculture.

*Corresponding author:

Sarah B. Aquino

ABSTRACT

Carrier materials are critical to the viability and functional delivery of microbial biofertilizers, directly influencing their efficacy in sustainable agriculture. Conventional carriers, such as soil mixed with wood charcoal, are becoming increasingly costly and scarce, prompting the need for alternative low-cost substrates. This study investigated whether locally abundant agro-wastes could serve as effective carriers for biofertilizer formulations. To assess the microbial viability of *Rhizobium tropici* and *Bacillus safensis* co-inoculated on agro-waste substrates—rice hull, coconut coir dust, coconut coir fiber, and corn cobs—and to compare their economic feasibility with traditional soil-charcoal carriers. Sterilized formulations of agro-waste carriers were prepared in three ratios and inoculated with standardized cultures of *R. tropici* and *B. safensis*. Microbial populations were quantified as colony forming units per gram (CFU/g) immediately and at 48 hours post-inoculation using serial dilution and selective agar plating. A direct cost analysis evaluated raw material expenses relative to conventional carriers. Rice hull in a ratio of 120g soil + 40g hull achieved the highest microbial population (3.1×10^9 CFU/g), significantly surpassing the viability threshold of 10^6 CFU/g. Coconut coir dust also supported substantial populations up to 5.3×10^8 CFU/g. In contrast, coconut coir fiber and corn cobs consistently failed to maintain viable counts. Economic analysis indicated that using agro-waste carriers reduced raw material costs by approximately ₱294 per 250 packets compared to soil-charcoal mixtures. Rice hull and coconut coir dust are effective, economical carrier substrates for biofertilizer formulations containing *R. tropici* and *B. safensis*. These findings support the integration of agro-waste carriers into localized biofertilizer production systems, promoting sustainable and cost-efficient agricultural practices.

Copyright©2025, Sarah B. Aquino and Larjan Kent M. Cuevas. 2025. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Citation: Sarah B. Aquino and Larjan Kent M. Cuevas. 2025. "Performance of *Rhizobium tropici* and *Bacillus safensis* on Agro-Waste Substrates: Viability and Economic Feasibility as Alternatives to Soil-Charcoal Carrier". *International Journal of Current Research*, 17, (07), 33711-33715.

INTRODUCTION

Soil fertility management is crucial for sustainable agriculture and food security. Conventional farming's reliance on synthetic fertilizers has led to ecological issues, prompting a shift towards more sustainable practices¹. Organic amendments and bio-fertilizers offer alternatives that enhance soil structure, nutrient availability, and microbial activity while reducing environmental impacts^{1,2}. Ecological intensification, which integrates ecosystem services into crop production, can help meet rising agricultural demands while minimizing negative environmental effects³. Organic fertilizers and cover crops improve soil health by enhancing physical, chemical, and biological properties, promoting beneficial microorganisms, and contributing to nutrient cycling and soil stability⁴. This integrated approach to soil fertility management not only supports sustainable food production but also contributes to

climate change mitigation through increased carbon sequestration and reduced reliance on chemical inputs^{1,4}. Biofertilizers are formulations containing living microorganisms that promote plant growth by increasing nutrient availability when applied to seeds, plants, or soil^{5,6}. They enhance soil fertility through processes like nitrogen fixation, phosphorus solubilization, and growth-promoting substance synthesis⁵. Unlike chemical fertilizers, biofertilizers are eco-friendly, non-toxic, and improve soil physicochemical and biological properties^{5,6}. They play a crucial role in sustainable agriculture by enhancing soil microbial diversity, improving soil structure, and contributing to carbon sequestration⁷. Biofertilizers also help plants tolerate abiotic and biotic stresses⁶. Despite their benefits, challenges such as limited awareness, inconsistent performance, and inadequate regulatory frameworks hinder widespread adoption⁷. Future

research should focus on improving formulation techniques and conducting long-term impact studies on soil health⁷.

Role and promise of microbial biofertilizers

Microbial biofertilizers offer a sustainable alternative to chemical fertilizers, enhancing soil fertility and crop productivity while minimizing environmental impacts^{7,8}. These formulations contain beneficial microorganisms like nitrogen-fixing bacteria, phosphate-solubilizing bacteria, and mycorrhizal fungi, which improve nutrient availability through various mechanisms⁹. Biofertilizers contribute to long-term soil health by fostering microbial diversity, improving soil structure, and increasing organic matter content⁷. They also promote plant growth by synthesizing growth-regulating substances and suppressing soil-borne diseases^{8,9}. Despite their advantages, challenges such as limited awareness, inconsistent performance, and inadequate regulatory frameworks hinder widespread adoption⁷. Recent advancements in biofertilizer technology, including multi-functional formulations and microbial consortia, show promise in improving their efficacy^{7,10}.

Critical importance of carriers in biofertilizer formulations

Carrier materials play a crucial role in biofertilizer formulations, affecting microbial viability and effectiveness during storage and application. Ideal carriers should support high microbial populations, be cost-effective, and environmentally friendly¹¹. Various materials have been explored as carriers, including clay soil, fly-ash, press mud, and lignite, with some formulations maintaining microbial populations up to six months¹². Vermicast has shown promise as a carrier, increasing bacterial survival compared to charcoal¹³. Lantana charcoal, derived from Lantana camara biomass, has emerged as a novel carrier material for *Azotobacter chroococcum*, demonstrating high water-holding capacity, neutral pH, and superior microbial support during storage¹⁴. These studies highlight the ongoing research to develop effective, sustainable carrier materials for biofertilizers, addressing challenges such as maintaining microbial viability and reducing environmental impacts associated with traditional carriers like wood charcoal and garden soil.

Agro-waste valorization as a sustainable alternative

Agricultural waste valorization presents a sustainable solution to manage the vast quantities of residues generated globally. These wastes, including rice husks, coconut fiber, and crop residues, can be transformed into valuable products, aligning with circular economy principles^{15,16}. Agro-wastes serve as effective carriers for microbial inoculants, supporting beneficial bacterial populations and enhancing soil fertility¹⁷. Various conversion techniques can produce activated carbons for environmental remediation, energy storage, and crop productivity improvement¹⁶. Additionally, agricultural wastes can be utilized to create biofuels, biofertilizers, bio-plastics, and other value-added products¹⁸. This approach not only addresses waste management challenges but also contributes to sustainable agriculture, mitigates climate change, and supports the bioeconomy^{15,18}. Implementing these strategies can significantly reduce environmental pollution and fossil fuel dependence while promoting agricultural sustainability

Focus of this study

This research explores the potential of microbial biofertilizers to enhance crop productivity while reducing chemical fertilizer use. *Bacillus safensis* and *Bacillus siamensis* strains demonstrated phosphorus solubilization, nitrogen fixation, and phytohormone production capabilities, promoting plant growth when used in combination¹⁹. Various nitrogen-fixing and potassium-solubilizing bacteria have been identified as potential biofertilizers²⁰. Bioengineering approaches can improve the efficiency of nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilization, and potassium mobilization in microbial communities²¹. In a study on common beans, inoculation with *Rhizobium tropici*, especially when combined with other beneficial microorganisms like *Trichoderma harzianum*, enhanced nodule formation and improved agronomic parameters. Co-inoculation with *Azospirillum brasilense* significantly increased grain yield, particularly in clayey soil with reduced NPK fertilization, suggesting the potential for sustainable agriculture with decreased reliance on mineral fertilizers²².

Objectives and broader relevance

This study aimed to evaluate the viability of co-inoculated *R. tropici* and *B. safensis* on four locally abundant agro-waste substrates—rice hull, coconut coir dust, coconut coir fiber, and corn cobs—each tested in three formulation ratios. Additionally, an economic analysis compared the direct material costs of these agro-waste carriers with conventional soil-charcoal systems. By identifying effective, low-cost alternatives, the study seeks to provide practical solutions that can be adopted by local farmers, cooperatives, and community-based biofertilizer production units, thereby contributing to more resilient, ecologically sound farming systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and rationale

The experiment was structured to comprehensively assess both the biological and economic viability of using agro-waste carriers. A factorial approach was employed, testing four carrier types across three formulation ratios, allowing a robust comparison of how carrier composition influenced microbial survival.

Carrier preparation

The agro-waste materials—rice hull, coconut coir dust, coconut coir fiber, and chopped corn cobs—were collected from local farms and agro-industrial processing sites. Each material was sun-dried to reduce moisture content and then ground to achieve reasonably uniform particle sizes, improving homogenization with soil and inoculum. Three carrier formulations were prepared for each material:

- 80g sterilized garden soil + 80g agro-waste (Ratio 1)
- 120g sterilized garden soil + 40g agro-waste (Ratio 2)
- 160g agro-waste alone, no soil (Ratio 3)

All mixtures were sterilized using a conventional autoclave at 121°C for 30 minutes to eliminate background microbial populations, ensuring that subsequent counts reflected only the introduced inoculants.

Inoculum preparation and application: Pure cultures of *R. tropici* were grown in Yeast Mannitol Broth (YMB) for nitrogen-fixers, while *B. safensis* cultures were maintained in parallel in Pikovskaya's broth for phosphate-solubilization and Aleksandrow's broth for potassium mobilization. After reaching microbial growth phase, 20 mL of *R. tropici* and 20 mL of combined *B. safensis* cultures were mixed to create a 40 mL inoculum. This was uniformly incorporated into each 160g carrier formulation under aseptic conditions.

Microbial enumeration

Microbial viability was assessed immediately after inoculation and again at 48 hours. Samples were serially diluted and plated on Nutrient Agar to calculate *R. tropici* and *B. safensis*. Colony forming units per gram (CFU/g) were calculated using standard plate count techniques, with results averaged over three replicate plates per sample.

Economic analysis

To determine the feasibility of scaling these formulations, a cost analysis compared the direct raw material expenses for producing 250 biofertilizer packets using agro-waste carriers versus the traditional garden soil and wood charcoal blend. Local market rates in Ilagan City, Isabela were used to compute total expenses, enabling a straightforward cost comparison.

RESULTS

Microbial viability across carrier formulations

Results revealed significant variability in microbial survival depending on carrier type and ratio.

- Rice hull consistently exceeded the critical viability threshold of 10^6 CFU/g across all ratios, corroborating previous findings²³. Notably, Ratio 2 (120 g soil + 40 g rice hull) yielded the highest microbial counts, reaching 3.1×10^9 CFU/g. Ratio 3 (pure rice hull) also performed well at 4.8×10^8 CFU/g, underscoring rice hull's intrinsic suitability as a microbial carrier due to its high porosity and moisture retention capacity.
- Coconut coir dust demonstrated moderate effectiveness, with Ratio 3 (pure coir dust) achieving 5.3×10^8 CFU/g and Ratio 2 at 3.4×10^8 CFU/g, which is consistent with previous observations²⁴. However, Ratio 1 did not sustain sufficient populations, possibly due to dilution effects from higher soil content or uneven moisture distribution that may have compromised microbial survival.
- In contrast, coconut coir fiber and corn cobs consistently failed to support viable microbial populations across all tested ratios, with counts falling below detectable limits. This outcome likely reflects the presence of inhibitory phenolic compounds in coir fiber as previously documented²⁵, and the dense, compact structure of corn cobs which restricts aeration and microbial colonization.

Initial short-term viability

Within 48 hours post-inoculation, rice hull and coconut coir dust maintained robust populations, indicating minimal immediate die-off. These carriers effectively stabilized the

introduced microbes, preserving populations well above the threshold required for biofertilizer quality standards.

Economic assessment

The cost comparison revealed dramatic differences. Producing 250 packets of biofertilizer carrier using the soil-charcoal mixture required approximately ₱318.75, primarily due to the high price of wood charcoal. In contrast, formulations based on agro-wastes cost only ₱25.00, representing a savings of ₱293.75. This 92% reduction in carrier material costs highlights a compelling economic incentive for adopting agro-waste substrates.

DISCUSSION

This study underscores the potential of agricultural waste products as alternative carriers for microbial biofertilizers. Rice husk exhibited particularly promising characteristics, including low moisture content, high porosity, and strong water absorption capacity, which collectively supported microbial growth and plant development²³. Coconut coir dust also proved moderately effective, especially in pure formulations, consistent with earlier findings that demonstrated its ability to enhance microbial survival in crop systems²⁴. However, the inconsistent performance observed across different ratios highlights the need for optimizing parameters such as moisture content and implementing pre-treatment strategies to mitigate inhibitory phenolic compounds²⁵. Conversely, coconut coir fiber and corn cobs were unsuitable under the conditions tested. The likely causes include phenolic toxicity and poor structural compatibility for inoculant adherence, consistent with findings in bioremediation studies where certain lignocellulosic substrates inhibited microbial colonization²⁶.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that rice hull, especially in a formulation of 120g soil + 40g hull, serves as an optimal carrier for co-inoculated *R. tropici* and *B. safensis*, achieving CFU counts surpassing 3.1×10^9 . Coconut coir dust also emerged as a viable alternative under specific ratios. These agro-waste carriers not only ensured superior microbial viability but also reduced carrier costs by over 90% compared to traditional soil-charcoal mixtures. By integrating agro-waste substrates into local biofertilizer production, this approach promotes environmentally sustainable, economically accessible, and community-driven nutrient management systems. Future studies should explore long-term shelf-life under ambient storage and validate field performance across multiple crop systems, paving the way for widespread adoption of this low-cost, eco-friendly technology. Economically, the shift from soil-charcoal to agro-waste carriers presents a transformative opportunity for resource-constrained farming communities. Beyond reducing input costs, this strategy valorizes local residues that otherwise contribute to environmental burdens, effectively closing nutrient loops and supporting circular bioeconomies.

Glossary of Abbreviations

CFU – Colony Forming Unit
 DA – Department of Agriculture
 LGU – Local Government Unit
 RFO – Regional Field Office

REFERENCES

1. Singh S, Devi NB, D D, Kumar A, Singh S, Tyagi G, *et al.* Soil fertility management: Role of organic amendments and bio-fertilizers: A review. *International Journal of Research in Agronomy* [Internet]. 2024 Dec 1;7(12):766–72. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.33545/2618060x.2024.v7.i12j.2253>
2. Bargaz A, Lyamlouli K, Chtouki M, Zeroual Y, Dhiba D. Soil microbial resources for improving fertilizers efficiency in an integrated plant nutrient management system. *Frontiers in Microbiology* [Internet]. 2018 Jul 31;9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.01606>
3. Bommarco R, Kleijn D, Potts SG. Ecological intensification: harnessing ecosystem services for food security. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* [Internet]. 2012 Nov 12;28(4):230–8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2012.10.012>
4. Khan MT, Aleinikovienė J, Butkevičienė LM. Innovative Organic Fertilizers and cover crops: Perspectives for Sustainable agriculture in the Era of Climate Change and Organic Agriculture. *Agronomy* [Internet]. 2024 Dec 1;14(12):2871. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy14122871>
5. García-Fraile P, Menéndez E, Rivas R. Role of bacterial biofertilizers in agriculture and forestry. *AIMS Bioengineering* [Internet]. 2015 Jan 1;2(3):183–205. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3934/bioeng.2015.3.183>
6. Chaudhary P, Singh S, Chaudhary A, Sharma A, Kumar G. Overview of biofertilizers in crop production and stress management for sustainable agriculture. *Frontiers in Plant Science* [Internet]. 2022 Aug 23;13. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.930340>
7. P Keerthanam, P A, Singh V, Bhargavi R, Pujitha N, Anusha T, *et al.* The Role of Biofertilizers in soil health Improvement and Sustainable Farming: A Comprehensive review. *Archives of Current Research International* [Internet]. 2025 May 1;25(5):163–79. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.9734/acri/2025/v25i51196>
8. Nosheen S, Ajmal I, Song Y. Microbes as biofertilizers, a potential approach for sustainable crop production. *Sustainability* [Internet]. 2021 Feb 9;13(4):1868. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041868>
9. Thomas L, Singh I. Microbial biofertilizers: types and applications. In: *Soil biology* [Internet]. 2019. p. 1–19. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-18933-4_1
10. Sharma AK. Biofertilizer – a key player in enhancing soil fertility and agricultural sustainability. *International Journal of Agriculture Environment and Biotechnology* [Internet]. 2023 Jun 23;16(2). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.30954/0974-1712.02.2023.10>
11. Ariani NS, Simarmata T. A Systematic Review: Current Technology of Solid Carrier Formulation to improve Viability and Effectiveness of Nitrogen-Fixing Inoculant. *Jurnal Agribisnis Dan Agrowisata (Journal of Agribusiness and Agritourism)* [Internet]. 2023 Apr 30;34(1):48. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.24198/agrikultura.v34i1.43138>
12. Tabassam T, Sultan T, Akhtar ME, Mahmood-Ul-Hassan M, Ali A. Suitability of different formulated carriers for sustaining microbial shelf life. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research* [Internet]. 2015 Jan 1;28(2):143–51. Available from: <https://www.cabdirect.org/cabdirect/abstract/20163218102>
13. N P, T AR. Comparative study of vermicast and charcoal used as a carrier inoculums to the biofertilizer preparation. *Environmental Science, Agricultural and Food Sciences* [Internet]. Available from: http://bmjournals.com/uploads/89f1fc857b2b3b76a01abc2cd963869216f98044a508dc1e521863df7473a593/manuscript/2014-06-08_09-52-18-pmbt1405.pdf
14. Mankar MK, Sharma US, Sahay S. Lantana charcoal as potent carrier material for *Azotobacter chroococcum*. *Die Bodenkultur Journal of Land Management Food and Environment* [Internet]. 2021 Jun 1;72(2):83–91. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2478/boku-2021-0008>
15. Puglia D, Pezzolla D, Gigliotti G, Torre L, Bartucca ML, Del Buono D. The Opportunity of Valorizing Agricultural Waste, Through Its Conversion into Biostimulants, Biofertilizers, and Biopolymers. *Sustainability* [Internet]. 2021 Mar 3;13(5):2710. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052710>
16. Hoang T, Van Anh N, Yusuf M, A MAS, Subramanian Y, Nam NH, *et al.* Valorization of Agriculture Residues into Value-Added Products: A Comprehensive Review of Recent Studies. *The Chemical Record* [Internet]. 2024 Jul 25;24(8). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/tcr.202300333>
17. Sadasivam KV, Tyagi RK, Ramarethinam S. Evaluation of some agricultural wastes as carriers for bacterial inoculants. *Agricultural Wastes* [Internet]. 1986 Jan 1;17(4):301–6. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-4607\(86\)90138-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-4607(86)90138-1)
18. Koul B, Yakoob M, Shah MP. Agricultural waste management strategies for environmental sustainability. *Environmental Research* [Internet]. 2021 Oct 25;206:112285. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.112285>
19. Altimira F, Godoy S, Arias-Aravena M, Araya B, Montes C, Castro JF, *et al.* Genomic and Experimental Analysis of the Biostimulant and Antagonistic Properties of Phytopathogens of *Bacillus safensis* and *Bacillus siamensis*. *Microorganisms* [Internet]. 2022 Mar 22;10(4):670. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10040670>
20. Vishwakarma D, Thakur JK, Gupta SC. A study on nitrogen fixing ability of soil isolates and quantitative estimation of K solubilization by soil and plant isolates. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* [Internet]. 2017 Dec 10;6(12):2641–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2017.612.305>
21. Ghorai P, Ghosh D. Ameliorating the performance of NPK biofertilizers to attain sustainable agriculture with special emphasis on bioengineering. *Bioresource Technology Reports* [Internet]. 2022 Jun 12;19:101117. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2022.101117>
22. De Souza LFR, De Souza Júnior NC, Fernandes GC, Ito WCN, Barbosa MC, Freitas LB, *et al.* Response of *Phaseolus vulgaris* to the Use of Growth-Promoting Microorganisms Associated with the Reduction of NPK Fertilization in Tropical Soils: Clayey Oxisol and Sandy Ultisol. *Agriculture* [Internet]. 2024 Dec 29;15(1):63.

- Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture15010063>
23. Ogbo F, Odo M. Potential of rice husk and cassava peel as carriers for bio-fertilizer production. Nigerian Journal of Biotechnology [Internet]. 2011 Jan 1;23. Available from: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/njb/article/download/104521/94588>
24. Chromkaew Y, Kaomuangmoon T, Mawan N, Mukjang N, Khongdee N. Is coconut coir dust an efficient biofertilizer carrier for promoting coffee seedling growth and nutrient uptake? PeerJ [Internet]. 2023 Jun 14;11:e15530. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.15530>
25. Silveira EB, Rodrigues VJLB, Gomes AMA, Mariano RLR, Mesquita JCP. Pó de coco como substrato para produção de mudas de tomateiro. Horticultura Brasileira [Internet]. 2002 Jun 1;20(2):211–6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0102-05362002000200019>
26. Fletcher E, Baetz K. Multi-Faceted Systems Biology Approaches Present a Cellular Landscape of Phenolic Compound Inhibition in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology [Internet]. 2020 Oct 14;8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.539902>